

The Lived Experiences of Entrepreneurs with Disabilities in Vhembe Rural Areas, South Africa

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Abstract

Persons with disabilities still experience societal attitudinal challenges when wanting to participate in economic activities. Challenges related to social exclusion of these individuals include stigma and perceptions about disability in spite of legislation and policies that promote an inclusive society. The objective of the research reported on in this article was to determine the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities in the Vhembe district of Limpopo Province, South Africa. In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with six entrepreneurs with disabilities. An interview guide with a set of questions was utilised. Thematic analysis was conducted to identify emerging themes. Analysis of the interviews revealed three main themes pertaining to the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities, namely, access to adequate financial resources, language barriers, and prejudice and stereotypes. A deeper understanding was gained of the lived experiences of persons with disabilities when they participate in entrepreneurial development. The study contributes to the existing understanding of the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities, by foregrounding financial difficulties, inequality, prejudice, as well as a lack of financial resources and knowledge as the main challenges experienced by the participants. This study demonstrates the understanding of the experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities. The participants' knowledge will raise awareness about exclusion and challenges of persons with disabilities to realise inclusive participation in socioeconomic development.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, lived experiences, persons with disabilities, rural, South Africa

1. Introduction

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) recognises the existing value and potential contributions of people with disabilities to the overall well-being and diversity of their communities. It states that the ‘promotion of the full enjoyment’ by persons with disabilities of their human rights and fundamental freedom to fully participate in society will result in an enhanced sense of belonging and in significant advances in the human, social and economic development of society and the eradication of poverty (UN 2006). In support, the international and domestic policy on disability is cited in Article 9 of the UNCRPD (UN 2006). Strategic Pillar 5: Reducing economic vulnerability and releasing human capital, of the White Paper on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Department of Social Development [DSD] 2016) emphasises the rights of this group of people in society. The UNCRPD (UN 2006), defines persons with disabilities to include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments, which in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis.

Despite this acknowledgement of human rights, the reduction of inequality in terms of economic security for persons with disabilities and their families will require a concerted and coordinated effort by national and local level governments, departments, municipalities, employers, labour unions, financial institutions, statistical bodies, education and research institutions, organisations for people with disabilities, skills development agencies, regulatory bodies, institutions promoting democracy, as well as international development agencies (Louw et al. 2023). Positive change will only be possible when these role players work together to synergise legislation, policies, systems, programmes, services, and monitoring and regulatory mechanisms aimed at the creation of decent work, employment schemes, skills development, social protection, environmental accessibility, and the reduction of inequality (DSD 2016). As such, an elective effort is required to address the principles of the present Convention, in support of full and effective participation by these individuals, and inclusion of them in society, as per Article 3c of the Convention (UN 2006).

The South African government is also under pressure to correct the socioeconomic imbalances resulting from many decades of Apartheid, especially since the rise of democracy in 1994 (Pooe, Mafini & Makhubele 2015). Even though South African economic policy places a high value on entrepreneurship (Chinomona & Maziriri 2015), the government has not been able to solve the socioeconomic issues of high unemployment and poverty reduction because of certain constraints that may also hamper entrepreneurship (Agbenyegah 2013). The constraints are an inability to access adequate financial resources, poor opportunities for skills development, and prejudice and discrimination. For instance, in South Africa entrepreneurial activities have shown a gradual decline over the years compared to other developing countries (Agbenyegah 2013). Consistent with the findings, Ijatuyi et al (2022) similarly state that South Africa consistently ranks poorly in the global entrepreneurship monitor survey in terms of entrepreneurial activity. It therefore seems clear that South Africa is not producing a sufficient entrepreneurial economy, with entrepreneurs facing difficulty in economically developing, growing and existing (Herrington & Coduras 2019). The authors identify lack of skills and opportunities due to low levels and quality of education to be able to participate actively in the economy. If this can be addressed, employment opportunities

may be created, markets can be expanded, production increased and communities revitalised (Morel & Dorpalen 2023).

1.1 Entrepreneurship as a possibility for persons with disabilities

Persons with disabilities represent a fair portion of the world population, accounting for an estimated 15% of the global population (Shanimon & Hameedu 2014). According to the latest national census report for South Africa, approximately 7,5% of the population live with a form of impairment (Statistics South Africa 2016), even though this indication may reflect an under-reporting of the true cases in the country, due to stigma and limitations in terms of measurement tools (Maart et al. 2019). This group of people are often required to cope with negative prevailing social perceptions, a lack of sufficient knowledge and training, as well as gender inequality (Gómez-Trigueros et al. 2021).

Krahn et al. (2015) are of the opinion that this group of people share the experience of living with significant limitations in functioning and, as a result, often experience exclusion from equal participation in their communities. Exclusion is a painful experience that will have both temporary and long-term damaging effects on the state of being of the person excluded from others (Delbosc & Currie 2011; Klompas & Ross 2004; Krahn et al. 2015; Tobias & Mukhopadhyay 2017). It goes without saying that it is crucial to view the experiences of persons with disabilities who are confronted with such negative experiences on an ongoing basis in their efforts to achieve equal status with others in society (Hammel et al. 2015).

Closely aligned, the White Paper on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities was endorsed by the President of South Africa in 2016, who described disability inclusion as follows (DSD, 2016):

‘Inclusion is regarded as a universal human right and aims at embracing the diversity of all people irrespective of race, gender, disability, or any other differences. It is about full participation, opportunities and [removal of prejudice]. It is about inclusion: feeling respected, considered to be important for who you are; feeling a level of supportive energy and agreement from others to fully participate in community with no constraint. Inclusion implies a change from an ‘individual change model’ to a ‘system change model’ that emphasises that society has to understand that each individual is unique. This includes a fundamental change in approach from the ‘specialness’ of people to the nature of society and its ability to respond to a wide range of individual differences and needs. Inclusion is the ultimate objective of mainstreaming’.

Vashishth and Jhamb (2021) suggest that persons with disabilities may pursue a career in entrepreneurship and may even be more successful than entrepreneurs without a disability. According to the authors things that make entrepreneurs with disabilities more successful include, but are not limited to, specific professional competencies, experience in the sector, ability to learn new things in business practice, ability to recognise opportunities, and socioemotional competencies. Magaji (2019) is of the view that South Africa does not suffer from a lack of

creative spirit, but rather from a lack of sufficient business education and entrepreneurial skills training that can empower individuals to pursue such a career in an enabling environment. A study by Choto et al. (2014) similarly points to limitations in skills development, indicating that the public school system in South Africa does not support business as a profession, but views business as something that people can do when they fail to secure a job and hold a profession. Entrepreneurship is an option for persons with disabilities in South Africa because it could assist to eradicate poverty and unemployment. The support and limitations for entrepreneurship is limited by poor education, lack of financial support from financial institutions, lack of training, negative attitude by communities, and competition among entrepreneurs.

1.2 Entrepreneurial pathways often pursued by persons with disabilities

Despite the apparent lack of recognition of the possibilities of entrepreneurship as a career in South Africa, this career path may provide a solution to persons with disabilities who would like to enter the business world and earn a living in this sector of society (Mustaffa et al. 2020). Furthermore, Alshebami (2023) asserts that entrepreneurship will, to some extent, control the financial status of a country, allowing individuals with opportunities to succeed in life. In this regard, Fatoki and Garwe (2010) note that, given the failure of the formal and public sector to absorb the growing number of job seekers in South Africa, greater emphasis has fallen on entrepreneurship and its potential to support economic growth and income generation opportunities. Consistent with this view, Emirie et al. (2020) assert that some groups of people may find this option to be especially suitable, such as women, young people, persons with disabilities, people from ethnic minority groups, and those who are unemployed or who reside in rural areas, because there is a lack of job opportunities and people believe that entrepreneurship could be a solution to poverty and unemployment.

Park et al. (2022) concur with this view and indicate that entrepreneurship has become an important tool for many to relieve hunger and address the challenge of poverty. More specifically, increased empowerment of persons with disabilities may help them to earn a living and participate in fields together with others without disabilities, thereby addressing the experiences of exclusion. Against this background, we conducted research on the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities, in terms of the challenges they face on a daily basis when pursuing this career option within a rural setting.

1.3 How a rural setting may impact entrepreneurship for people in general and those with disabilities

In a rural setting, persons with disabilities experience significant challenges, in comparison to their equals in urban areas. They are less likely to have attended school or to be employed and they are often left behind in rural development interventions (WHO 2022). The financial support challenges experienced by entrepreneurs with disabilities can be ascribed to bureaucracy and red tap which means processes and procedures for approval of that support take quite a long time. The following describes the process of applying for the establishment of a business. The application is approved by the traditional leader who refers it to the Chief for approval. Thereafter, it is submitted to the municipality. Financial support from financial institutions would need a form of security from the applicant to approve a loan. Some business establishments are located far from where the stock could be

obtained. The transport could be expensive when they want to transport goods from towns and cities to the village. This implies that they would have a shortage of stock time to time and this could demoralised consumers.

2. Research method and design

A qualitative research approach was followed to explore the lived experiences of six entrepreneurs with disabilities in the Vhembe district, Limpopo Province, South Africa. The choice of a qualitative approach was nested in the purpose of the study, which concerned the lived experiences of people, based on personal meaning making and perceptions. Based on Kumar's descriptive characteristics of qualitative research (2011), namely, an unstructured, flexible and open approach to enquiry, this enabled us to obtain an in-depth understanding of the participants' first-hand experiences.

A case study design was accordingly employed (Merriam 2009). According to Cohen et al. (2013), a case study design has the advantage of data being drawn from people's lived experiences in order to construct reality. In this study, we specifically aimed to obtain an in-depth understanding of the lived experienced of entrepreneurs with disabilities. An exploratory case study was used. Merriam (2009) outlines three approaches: (a) Historical and Observational, (b) Intrinsic and Instrumental, and (c) Multisite case studies. The authors of this article employed an exploratory case study in the context of lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities in Vhembe rural areas.

An exploratory case study is used to develop an initial understanding of the programme or phenomenon of interest. The focus is on discovery for the purpose of obtaining an empirically based introduction to the structure, dynamics and context of the subject of interest. A case-study also allows for the use of multiple sources of data, namely, interviews, documentation, archival records, direct observations, participant-observation, and physical artefacts-

3. Study population and sampling strategy

Six entrepreneurs with disabilities were conveniently sampled as participants. The participants were aged 30 to 55 years at the time of data collection, with three being male and three females.

The participants all lived in the Vhembe district of Limpopo at the time of the study, and all were Tshivenda speaking. To ensure anonymity, descriptions of the participants are used, with pseudonyms. An overview of the participants is provided in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Characteristics of participants (n = 6)

Participant	Gender	Age	Type of disability	Area of entrepreneurship
A	Female	48	Partially sighted	Spaza shop selling groceries, sweets, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables
B	Female	36	One leg amputated (participant used crutches)	Spaza shop selling groceries, sweets, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables
C	Female	47	One hand amputated (participant used artificial hand)	Spaza shop selling groceries, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables
D	Male	38	Loss of function in hands and legs (participant used wheelchair)	Spaza shop selling groceries, sweets, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables
E	Male	39	Quadriplegic paralysed from shoulders down	Spaza shop selling groceries, sweets, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables.
F	Male	39	Participant using artificial limbs and crutches	Spaza shop selling groceries, snacks, sweets, fruit and vegetables

4. Data collection

Data was collected through in-depth semi-structured face-to face interviews. For data documentation purposes the participants were requested to provide informed consent to participate in the study as well as for the interviews to be recorded. The participants with low vision were provided with forms in large print format. The researchers also made themselves available in case participants with low vision needed assistance with completing the forms. Recordings and verbatim transcripts of the interviews were kept in a secure place to which only the researchers had access.

Interviews were conducted at the homes of the participants and lasted around 60 minutes each. An interview schedule guided the interviews, taking into account the style proposed by Bernard (2002), where participants are requested to narrate their experiences in a free-flowing manner (Neille 2020). In preparation for the interviews, sufficient time was spent on establishing trusting relationships with the participants and clarifying any questions or concerns (Hoel et al. 2021). In support of trustworthiness of the study, participants were sampled conveniently, clear explanations of the research process were provided, audio recordings were used, and an audit trail was kept (Sinha et al. 2021). Interview questions were used to obtain information from participants. The research question that guided the study was: What are the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities?

5. Data analysis

Thematic data analysis of entrepreneurs was done according to the approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006), who value thematic inductive analysis due to its flexibility and usefulness in providing rich, detailed, yet complex accounts of data. Accordingly, the following steps were executed to analyse the data: familiarising oneself with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming themes. Themes were furthermore reviewed to determine how some of these could be combined into broader themes or sub-themes (Daly-Smith, 2021 et al.)

6. Results

The participants in the study were persons with disabilities. The study revealed that those participants depended on their spaza shops and disability grant for a living. The study further revealed that all participants' efforts to seek financial support and skills development for their business from financial institutions had failed. The following three themes emerged, pertaining to the challenges experienced by entrepreneurs with disabilities in the Vhembe district of Limpopo, South Africa: access to adequate financial resources; communication barriers; and prejudice and stereotypes. These themes are discussed in this section and substantiated with direct quotations from the interview data.

6.1 Theme 1: Access to adequate financial resources

The participants in the study were persons with disabilities. The study revealed that those participants depended on their spaza shops and disability grant for a living. The study further revealed that all participants' efforts to seek financial support for their business from financial institutions had failed:

"I have approached different institutions for start-up capital with no success. Let me tell you, I depend on my disability grant and which is not enough, I have saved my start-up capital for twelve months. I was saving two hundred rand per month. It was not easy at all because my disability grant is for my basic needs like buying food for my family" (PA, female, 48 years old).

"I submitted my application for funding in one of the institutions which supports youth two years back after I heard about the call application on the radio till today no response yet. I had hope because persons with disabilities were encouraged to apply. I was surprised to realise that from my village some of the youth received funding" (PB, female, 36 years old).

"I approached my nearest bank for start-up capital, they told me that I don't qualify for loan because I don't have security. I am telling you these banks won't loan you even a cent. Where do get security because I have just started establishing my spaza shop. This is a way of excluding persons with disabilities" (PE, male, 39 years old).

"In 2019 I was told to revise my business proposal four times in one of the institutions. I am still waiting for the response till today. It is my wish to extend my spaza shop, my disability grant is not enough for my family. I am married with two children and my wife is unemployed" (PD, male, 38 years old).

"No one and no oneis taking persons with disabilities serious we are human beings we need to work for our families. We are not considered as South African, when it is time for voting we are given first preference I am not going to waste my vote and my time to vote to the next coming election because we are not recognised when we need her" (PF, male, 39 years old).

"I remember when I approached one of the banks which I learnt that support small entrepreneurship. I could not expand my business. My application was disapproved because I don't have any security" (PC, female, 47 years old).

Experiences such as these seemingly left the participants with feelings of frustration and of being excluded. They had to depend on themselves to start and maintain any small business effort, often being forced to utilise their disability grant to attempt to earn a living, rather than to provide for their basic needs.

6.2 Theme 2: Communication barriers, lack of education/training opportunities

English was identified as a major challenge by the entrepreneurs who participated in the study. According to the participants, language and specifically their (limited) proficiency in English resulted in them not being able to participate in and fully benefit from, for example, economic empowerment workshops and training opportunities. They mentioned their own schooling and poor proficiency in English as barriers, with one participant referring to her inability to communicate efficiently due to her visual impairment and the lack of Braille-translated material. The following explanations provide supportive evidence of their experiences:

“Sadly, I did not go to school and that was not my choice, and I cannot read and write English. It was not my choice for not going to school because my parents did not send me to school. It is very sad to be discriminated and miss empowerment entrepreneurship opportunities because of language barrier. I must tell you that I could not attend two weeks business management training which was conducted last year by one of the Government departments. I was asked to submit grade twelve certificate as one of the requirements to attend the training, it hurt me because I could not submit that certificate” (PB, female, 36 years old).

“It was painful when I withdraw my participation from five days youth economic empowerment training in 2018 because the facilitator was conducting the training in English. I remember when I raise my concern of communication barrier, I was told to arrange my own translator. I could not succeed because it was going to be expensive to pay double for the transport. That was a negative attitude. This is not fair.....I believe that the training was an important skill which will help me to make an impact to my business-like other entrepreneurship” (PE, male, 39 years old).

“I am partially sighted and there was no provision of braille manuals materials when I participated to financial management workshop. I was told that braille manual will be arranged soon. It is sad because I was not treated equally like other participants because I have not yet received my braille manual.” (PA, female, 48 years old).

6.3 Theme 3: Prejudice and discrimination

All six participants mentioned experiences of feeling prejudiced and discriminated against in trying to generate an income for their families. They referred to people avoiding them, not buying from their spaza shops and belittling them due to their disabilities, as captured in the following contributions. Societal beliefs and attitude that inform the prejudice and discrimination is that persons with disability are associated with curses, being bewitched which causes the disability, disease, dependence, and helplessness that motivate individuals from the community to fear, reject, and discriminate against persons with disabilities. Prejudice and discrimination practices meted against persons with disabilities include failure to make reasonable adjustments and being denied equal participation like other community members.

Prejudice and discrimination from the community encourages individuals to fear, reject, avoid, and discriminate against persons with disabilities. The following extracts from participants indicated that prejudice and discrimination:

“I remember the other day I announced as a way of advertising to our community meeting that 12kg maize mealie is now available to my spaza shop. One of the young women from my community told me that she like to come and buy because it is near to her house, but she can't because her mother once told her not to buy anything to my spaza shop. I asked her the reason, she told me that her mother once told her that I am having this disability because of I am a witch. When I buy from his shop I will give birth to a child with disability” (PC, female, 47 years old).

“I can't even explain the pain; they don't support my spaza shop because they fear my disability. My neighbour is pregnant..... I heard that she not buying from my shop because she is afraid that she may give birth to a child with disability” (PF, male, 39 years old).

“They are cruel ...is difficult for me and this has affected me a lot, because of this negative attitude. Being an entrepreneurship is my only hope to create job for myself because I could not get a job. I cannot continue because they tease my children about my disability and this is affecting my children. I feel rejected by this community” (PA, female, 48 years old).

“When they play with my children displaying negative behaviour by calling them names because of my disabilities. It is painful... My spaza shop is named penguin spaza because of my disability, can you believe it. These children are very cruel. I heard from my children that when they play with other children told them that your father walks like a penguin. I am only experiencing this because of my disability and lack of enough income which is a challenge. If I had a job, I wouldn't have experienced this attitude. I felt so belittled” (PB, female, 36 years old).

“I felt embarrassed and useless, really...I don't want to lie to you...I felt as if I am not existing in this world”. “I don't feel okay...it makes me angry for that matter” These negative attitudes and evictions are hurtful and take peace away from me within my heart” (PC, female, 47 years old).

“What's wrong with my appearance? I was born like this I cannot change myself.... I mean to change my disability. If they don't want to buy from my spaza shop is fine.... I have a huge responsibility to my family I am the provider to my family. I am a married man with five children, if we don't have food in the house, they look at me. In our culture the husband is the head of the family and I should be responsible for the family. How I wish to relocate to another village, unfortunately I don't have money” (PF, male, 39 years old).

All the participants' dependency on their disability grants compelled them to start spaza shops because they could afford to start and run the spaza shop with a small amount of money. The establishment of a district forum for entrepreneurs is important to advocate for partnerships with the district for opportunities which will assist persons

with disabilities with essential resources for the success of their spaza shops with knowledge and skills development for economic growth.

Other sources of data used for this study were mentioned under the methodology section. Documents reviewed, such as policies, indicate that persons with disabilities experience the same challenges as their abled bodied counterparts. Documents reviewed include Department of the Presidency (DOP) (2013); Department of Women, Children and People with Disabilities (DWCPD) (2013, as well as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) (United Nations [UN] 2006), and at national level, the Integrated National Disability Strategy (INDS) (Office of the Deputy President [OSDP] 1997), the National Development Plan 2030 (NDP) (DOP 2013) and the White Paper on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (WPRPD) and its accompanying implementation matrix (Department of Social Development [DSD] 2016). During the document analysis the authors decided on specific documents to analyse and these were mentioned above. Furthermore, the authors decided on the organisation of the information. This was done to ensure the authenticity of analysed documents. Biases were checked to be certain that the analysed documents promoted inclusion of entrepreneurs with disabilities and their experiences of unemployment, inferior education, poverty and lack of financial support. The other finding is that persons with disabilities experience stigma and stereotype challenges. Though good and relevant policies are in place and make specific provisions for women and persons with disabilities this is in theory and not practice.

Before the advent of democracy in 1994, Limpopo Province was known as the Northern Transvaal. During the early years of democracy, its name changed to Northern Province and Limpopo Province respectively. Limpopo Province is composed of five municipal districts Vhembe being one of them. Vhembe is composed of four local municipalities viz.: Musina, Thulamela, Collins Chabani and Makhado local municipality. Vhembe District municipality shares its borders with Zimbabwe, Greater Giyani and Capricorn District municipality. According to Maziriri and Chivandi (2020) Limpopo Province is by far the most rural province in the country, with 86.7 per cent of its population living in rural areas. Maziriri and Chivandi posit that the previously given figure is a strong indication that Limpopo's economy is relatively non-industrial, with its two primary sectors, agriculture and mining, accounting for the major share of the province's gross geographical product. Vhembe too, largely depends on these two economic sectors. Maziriri and Chivandi (2020) further opine that the province is ravaged by unemployment with a rate of 46 per cent, the lowest literacy levels (73.6 per cent) and the lowest Human Development Index and household income (55.8 per cent of the workforce earn less than R6500 per annum). Persons with disabilities in Limpopo Province in general and Vhembe district in particular, are not spared these challenges. This negative scenario is sufficient reason for small, medium and micro enterprises (SMME) support to be intensified at provincial, regional and municipal levels.

7. Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that entrepreneurs with disabilities surveyed in the Vhembe district of Limpopo, South Africa, experience several challenges in trying to get their small businesses off the ground and generate an income for their families. Firstly, the participants had to rely on their disability grants as they were unable to

secure financial support for their businesses from independent companies or institutions. More specifically, the participants indicated that they were rejected by financial institutions when they applied for financial support for socioeconomic development and growth. Institutions failing to support persons with disabilities confirms the notion that there is a lack of financial support for persons with disabilities. The authors interpret this as a form of prejudice and discrimination against persons with disabilities by financial institutions. This finding confirms the work of Ned and Lorenzo (2016), who contend that a disability grant is not sufficient to maintain a business and afford all the necessary aspects to sustain a healthy lifestyle. The South African disability grant programme remains one of the few means of financial support for households living in poverty (Curran et al 2021). Despite entrepreneurs with disabilities wanting to embark on small business ventures in their communities for them to be able to generate an income, the findings of this study indicate that such entrepreneurs will most likely have to use their disability grant to start and maintain their businesses, as the grant is not sufficient to support them and they are often left in a state of poverty. This finding also supports the work of Sadiki et al. (2021) who similarly note that disability grants are not sufficient to sustain families. Based on the finding that entrepreneurs with disabilities are seldom successful in obtaining external funding for their business ventures, the question remains as to how these people can make a living and take care of themselves and their families.

According to the World Health Organization Report on Disability (2011), persons with disabilities are often excluded from accessing the required finances to start new businesses due to a lack of collateral security, which is a prerequisite of financial institutions. Hästbacka et al. (2016) as well as Matsaure et al. (2020) confirm that entrepreneurs with disabilities will experience challenges in accessing external funding, despite finances being the “life blood” of any enterprise, whether it is big or small (Muturi & Njeru 2019). All the participants in our study agreed that they experienced barriers in terms of accessibility to funds and support from financial institutions. Negative attitudes were identified by the participants as yet another underlying barrier, as they experienced the government and some financial institutions as not seeing persons with disabilities, who cannot provide security for a loan, as an economically wise investment. This finding aligns with the work of Cooney and Licciardi (2019) who assert that financial institutions are not geared to support entrepreneurs, especially those with disabilities.

Be that as it may, when entrepreneurs with disabilities realise that the disability grant is not enough to sustain their families, they may start looking to external agencies for financial support. Nyanga argues (2013) that it is imperative for the local government and financial institutions to come forward and assist such entrepreneurs with easy access to, for example, loans, but this is not the current reality in South Africa. According to Mauchi et al. (2014), this lack of access to capital and credit schemes and the constraints of financial systems, pose hindrances to people wanting to pursue entrepreneurial ideas and economic development. The finding further aligns with the work of Seirlis and Swartz (2006), who confirm that commercial banks and lending houses will more often than not refrain from lending money to entrepreneurs, who cannot support their idea or dream with collateral or security should they require finances in order to set up their business. These financial barriers contribute to the participants’ feelings of being excluded as well as to economic hardship for them and their families. South Africa launched White Paper on the Rights of People with Disabilities (WPRPD) by the President of South Africa in 2016 to promote inclusivity as follows (DSD 2016): Strategic Pillar 5: Reducing Economic Vulnerability and Realising

Human Capital of the WPRPD (DSD 2016). This White Paper emphasises that persons with disabilities must have access to adequate financial sources to cover the additional cost of living associated with disability. Policy makers must promote equal opportunities and embrace disability and human rights in their quest to ensure more constructive ideas that would empower persons with disabilities full and active participation in society.

The findings of our study furthermore confirm a study by Ladzani and Netswera (2009), who found that in rural areas of Limpopo, nearly 80% of all small enterprises experienced access to funding as a crucial obstacle. As a result, people's dignity may suffer (Sadiki et al. 2021) and any potential growth in the business they start may be stifled (Denny-Smith 2021). Despite entrepreneurs wanting to expand their businesses, they may, as a result, not be recognised and supported in reaching their goals. Even though calls to assist entrepreneurs with disabilities are enshrined in, among other things, Article 27(f) of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and Optional Protocol (United Nations 2017a), these people may still feel excluded due to experiencing difficulty in accessing financial support for reasons such as limited personal financial resources (savings, home ownership), poor education, lower employment rates, the concentration of disabled employees in low-paid occupations, poor credit rating after long-term benefit receipt, disinterest/discrimination on the part of bank and a lack of accessible information on sources of grants and loans (Bai, Cai & Qin 2021). The participants in this study confirmed experiences of being excluded, and as a result not only facing financial difficulty to survive, but also experiencing psychological stress. As such, continued investigation into the support offered to entrepreneurs with disabilities is required at all levels.

The second significant challenge experienced by the participants relates to communication and language forming a barrier when wanting to pursue a career as an entrepreneur. As noted by Kamil (2015), communication barriers can prevent people from accessing skills and development opportunities, which will in turn have a negative impact on economic development and opportunities to play an active role in society (Hammel et al. 2015; UN 2006). In this regard, Matli and Ngoepe ((2021) view the education and training system as a central limiting factor for entrepreneurship in South Africa. In addition to the negative impact on business operations, entrepreneurs may experience feelings of low self-worth, related mental health challenges and social exclusion, which points to a violation of fundamental human rights, as outlined in the UN's Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN, 2007).

In practice, this challenge resulted in the participants not being able to gain from entrepreneurship empowerment opportunities as they could not read and write in English. Entrepreneurship training programmes should be offered to persons with and without disabilities (Ginevra et al. 2022; Goyal et al. 2021). This argument closely aligns with the work of Lang et al. (2019), who state that recognition of the rights of persons with disabilities is still not integrated within implementation plans, budgetary allocations, enforcement mechanisms and disaggregated management information systems of the majority of institutions. Even though educational interventions such as workshops, structured discussions or showcasing of the work of entrepreneurs could be helpful in reducing prejudice and discrimination against entrepreneurs with disabilities, Sarker (2020), notes that the challenge of exclusion due to language barriers remains a reality in the South African context for people with disabilities. They

faced other challenges besides language that need to be discussed further, namely, a lack of financial support, poor education and not being members of business organisations.

The findings of the study indicate that the third challenge experienced by the participants, related to prejudice and stereotypes, impacted various aspects of their lives in terms of their lived experiences, participation in society, respect, dignity and recognition by the community. The entrepreneurs who participated experienced a range of negative emotions because of the negative attitude demonstrated to them by the community. The results show that participants A, B, C and F experienced social beliefs and attitudes that inform the prejudice and discrimination.

Disability is associated with a curse and with a lack of hygiene and poor hygiene standards, believing that even the products they are selling are dirty. Some community members do not even want to touch their money or products because they believe that their disability is contagious. Others believe that being in proximity to a person with disability could affect their unborn. Hence, they will shun business owned by persons with disabilities.

These findings support other research studies on marginalised groups, pointing to the stigmatisation of persons with disabilities (Bezyak, et al. 2021). Similarly, Byra and Domagała-Zyśk (2022) emphasise that such negative views may in turn negatively affect the self-esteem of individuals, while maintaining general trends of discrimination and social prejudice against persons with disabilities. Stigma associated with persons with disabilities is preserved in a different way and often results in their being excepted from educational and training opportunities, employment and livelihood opportunities, health and other public services, and full participation in all aspects of society, including decision-making. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) (United Nations (UN 2006) Article 9) promotes equal participation on an equal basis with others in all aspects of life including any services provided to the public and in rural areas.

It follows that prejudice and discrimination against persons with disabilities will result in an infringement of their beliefs, as well as their economic, political and social rights (United Nations, 2008), which in turn will hinder their full participation in society. The United Nations (2008) refers to this as the ‘silent crisis’ as it will not only affect individuals with disabilities and their families, but also the economic well-being of society. Regarding impairment and deprivation often resulting in higher levels of poverty and the effect of poverty on a family, the latter may in turn lead to limited access to assistive devices, accessible buildings and rehabilitation services that could support the participation of all individuals in society (Maart et al. 2019; Mitra 2018; World Health Organization 2002). In addition to experiencing such negative attitudes from society and the associated financial struggles, entrepreneurs with disabilities may feel distressed as they are not supported by society to contribute where they can (Jammaers & Williams 2021).

8. Recommendations

8.1 Access to adequate financial resources

It is recommended that the South African government make a concerted effort through various frameworks to facilitate and promote collaboration with local small, medium, and micro enterprises [SMMEs] businesses to

advance entrepreneurship among people with disabilities. Government and other stakeholders can extend their financial support in ensuring full and effective participation to economic development.

8.2 Communication barriers, lack of education/training opportunities

Government should provide formal training for all entrepreneurs with disabilities to equip them with knowledge and skills. Training should be conducted in entrepreneurs' own language so that all entrepreneurs can understand easily.

8.3 Prejudice and discrimination

Policy makers should promote equal opportunities and embrace disability and human rights in their quest to ensure more constructive ideas that empower entrepreneurs with disabilities full and active participation in society. The legislation and policies must play a prodigious role in overcoming marginalisation, discrimination, isolation, exclusion and prejudice of people with disabilities within the economic growth and income generation opportunities. Legislators, agencies, and entrepreneurship development consultants should capacitate persons with disabilities to increase entrepreneurship expertise for economic development and poverty eradication. Entrepreneurs with disabilities should establish forums that challenge attitudinal barriers, discrimination and inequality from financial institutions, government, and other stakeholders. Disability awareness campaigns and workshops should be conducted, so that entrepreneurs can interact. Entrepreneurs with disabilities must play an active and meaningful role in advocating for recognition in economic growth and integration. Stakeholders and role players must remove barriers through reasonable accommodation and educational development programmes. This study was about entrepreneurship of individuals with disabilities running spaza shops and the next study could be on other types and forms of businesses. This study could provide valuable knowledge for further studies.

9. Limitations of the study

The study explored the lived experience of entrepreneurs with disabilities in a rural South African setting. The participants were selected based on having disabilities and residing in the Vhembe district, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Therefore, the findings cannot be generalised to other districts in Limpopo. The experiences shared by participants outline vital issues affecting entrepreneurs with impairments that could inform further studies. To conclude, additional research studies are required to further confirm the findings of the study. As a limitation, the authors employed interviews and documents analysis. Perhaps other sources such as archival records, observations, artefacts, etc. could have provided this study with valuable information for further enhancement.

10. Conclusion

The findings of the study suggest that entrepreneurs with disabilities experience challenges on a broad spectrum when wanting to pursue this career pathway, namely financial difficulties, communication barriers, and prejudice

and stereotypes, which ultimately impact on their well-being and quality of life. A lack of basic services when wanting to become entrepreneurs may furthermore result in experiences of social exclusion from their communities. The findings of this study provide a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of entrepreneurs with disabilities, who are driven by a desire to be successful entrepreneurs and to be independent.

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